

Results of studying the fauna of Lepidoptera in the North Kazakhstan region (Republic of Kazakhstan) in 2019-2021

Ivan A. Zuban¹, Svyatoslav A. Knyazev²,
Nadezhda V. Schevchuk¹, Yuliya N. Korobeinikova¹

1 North Kazakhstan University named after M. Kozybayev, 86 Pushkina str., Petropavlovsk, 150000, Kazakhstan

2 Altai State University, 61 Lenina St, Barnaul, 656049, Russia

Corresponding author: Ivan A. Zuban (zuban_ia@mail.ru)

Academic editor: R. Yakovlev | Received 20 January 2022 | Accepted 6 April 2022 | Published 3 May 2022

<http://zoobank.org/2BD8B1F4-048A-4703-BD19-76D71ACD594C>

Citation: Zuban IA, Knyazev SA, Schevchuk NV, Korobeinikova YuN (2022) Results of studying the fauna of Lepidoptera in the North Kazakhstan region (Republic of Kazakhstan) in 2019-2021. Acta Biologica Sibirica 8: 115–128. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7700512>

Abstract

The article presents the results of studying the fauna of Lepidoptera in the North Kazakhstan region in the field seasons of 2019-2021. The annotated list includes 219 species, including 37 species given for the first time for the North Kazakhstan region.

Keywords

North Kazakhstan region, Lepidoptera, fauna, new data

Introduction

Previously published lists of Lepidoptera of the North Kazakhstan region included 520 species of butterflies and moths (Knyazev 2015; Knyazev and Zuban 2016; 2019). In the field seasons of 2019-2021, in order to study the distribution, as well as clarify the species composition of Lepidoptera, the authors conducted additional collections in the northeastern, central and northwestern parts of the region. Dur-

ing the specified period, 219 species of Lepidoptera were caught, including 37 species that were recorded for this region for the first time. These materials formed the basis for writing this article.

Material and methods

To collect material, the authors used standard methods: catching with an scoop-net; light trap (mercury lamp DRV-250); smelling baits from fermented beer and jam.

The systematic position of taxa in the list is given in accordance with the new edition of the Catalog of Lepidoptera of Russia (Sinev 2019). All specimens are stored in the collections of authors. New species for the territory of the region, marked with an asterisk (*).

Below is the list of collection points (Fig. 1):

1. Shandak – Shandak village and its environs, 54°26'08,3"N, 70°44'49,80"E;
2. Ekaterinovka – 0.5 km SE of Ekaterinovka village, 54°35'26.8"N 66°42'32.7"E;
3. Presnovka – 0.2 km NW of Presnovka village, 54°40'40.7"N 67°09'37.7"E;
4. Meshanskiy forest – forest park near the Petropavlovsk city, 54°55'45.3"N 69°08'17.3"E;
5. Ivanovka – Ivanovka village, 54°39'32,07"N, 68°55'48,30"E;
6. Budennoe – 0.2 km NW of Budennoye village, 54°37'05.1"N 66°30'09.7"E;
7. Tarangul – 0.7 km SW of Tarangul village, 54°10'10.9"N 68°26'05.1"E;
8. Dvinsk – Dvinsk village, 54°08'47.1"N 68°25'47.1"E;
9. Cherunovka – Cherunovka village, 54°02'43.9"N 67°58'51.3"E;
10. Beskuduk – Beskuduk village, 54°03'23.5"N 68°04'55.0"E;
11. Novouzenka – Novouzenka village, 54°02'39.2"N 68°39'05.3"E;
12. Korneevka – Korneevka village, 53°59'43.5"N 68°24'19.4"E;
13. Dzhambul – Dzhambul village, 53°50'21.5"N 68°32'31.5"E;
14. Iversk – Iversk village, 54°08'58.3"N 68°37'16.0"E.

Results

Family Depressariidae

1. **Agonopterix pallorella* (Zeller, 1839) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 28.06.2019.

Family Tortricidae

2. *Agapeta hamana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 10.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 14.07.2019.

Figure 1. Localities of Lepidoptera collection in the North Kazakhstan region.

Family Pyralidae

3. **Hypsopygia glaucinalis* (Linnaeus, 1758) - 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019.
4. **Pyralis farinalis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 06.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 15.06.19; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 14.07.2019.
5. *Oncocera semirubella* (Scopoli, 1763) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
6. **Myleois circumvolta* (Fourcroy, 1785) – 3 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.

Family Crambidae

7. *Calamotropha paludella* (Hübner, 1824) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 25.06.2019.
8. *Chrysoteuchia culmella* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 17.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
9. *Crambus perlellus* (Scopoli, 1763) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 28.06.2019.
10. *Schoenobius gigantellus* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 25.06.19; 4 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
11. *Elophila nymphaeata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 24.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 14.07.2019.
12. *Parapoynx stratiotata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 14.06.2019; 3 specimens, Dvinsk, 22.08.2021.
13. *Evergestis frumentalis* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 03.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
14. *Evergestis extimalis* (Scopoli, 1763) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 14.07.2019.

15. *Sitochroa verticalis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 16.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 28.06.19; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 11.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
16. *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hübner, 1796) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 28.06.2019.
17. **Eurrhynx hortulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 06.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 17.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 10.07.2019.
18. *Pleuroptya ruralis* (Scopoli, 1763) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 22.07.2019.
19. *Loxostege sticticalis* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 2 specimens, Tarangul, 09.08.2021.

Family Pterophoridae

20. **Pterophorus pentadactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Tarangul, 12.07.2021; 1 specimen, Yavlenka, 15.07.2021; 2 specimens, Beskuduk, 08.07.2021; 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019.
21. *Emmelina monodactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.10.2019; 2 specimens, Tarangul, 08.08.21; 1 specimen, Beskuduk, 10.08.2021.

Family HesperIIDae

22. *Carchardus alceae* (Esper, 1780) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 23.06.2021; 1 specimen, Shandak, 29.06.2021.
23. *Heteropterus morpheus* (Pallas, 1771) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 19.06.2019.
24. *Oclodes sylvanus* (Esper, 1778) – 1 ♂, Presnovka, 06.06.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul 09.06.2019.
25. *Pyrgus malvae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Tarangul, 12.06.2021.
26. *Thymelicus lineola* (Ochsenheimer, 1808) – 2 specimens, Shandak, 29.06.2021.

Family Papilionidae

27. *Papilio machaon* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 05.08.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 10.06.2021; 1 specimen, Cherunovka 05.06.2021; 1 specimen, Dvinsk, 02.07.2021; 1 specimen, Shandak, 5.07.2021; 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 24.07.2021.

Family Pieridae

28. *Leptidea sinapis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 2 specimens, Iversk, 28.05.2019; 2 specimens, Iversk, 04.06.2021; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 27.05.2021; 1 specimen, Shandak, 10.07.2021.
29. *Aporia crataegi* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 15.06.2019; 2 specimens, Yavlenka, 22.06.2021; 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 24.06.2021; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 24.06.2021; 2 specimens, Korneevka, 02.07.2021.
30. *Pieris brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 05.07.2019.

31. *Pieris rapae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 15.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 05.07.2019; 2 specimens, Tarangul, 12.07.2021; 1 specimen, Iversk, 13.07.2021; 1 specimen, Korneevka, 15.07.2021; 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2021.
32. *Pontia chloridice* (Hübner, 1813) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 05.08.2019.
33. *Pontia daplidice* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 04.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2021.
34. *Pontia edusa* (Fabricius, 1787) – 3 specimens, Tarangul, 24.07.2021; 2 specimens, Iversk, 02.08.2021.
35. *Pieris napi* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Pokrovka, 04.06.2021; 1 specimen, Beskuduk, 08.06.2021.
36. *Gonepteryx rhamni* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 2 specimens, Tarangul, 04.06.2021.
37. *Colias erate* (Esper, 1805) – 1 specimen, Iversk, 05.07.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 14.07.2021.
38. *Colias hyale* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 3 specimens, Tarangul, 28.06.2021; 2 specimens, Iversk, 28.06.2021; 2 specimens, Novouzenka, 03.07.2021; 1 specimen, Shandak, 3.08.2021.

Family Lycaenidae

39. **Thecla betulae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 ♀, Presnovka, 26.07.2019; 1 ♀, Ivanovka, 04.09.2019.
40. *Lycaena dispar* (Haworth, 1802) – 1 specimen, Tarangul, 07.07.2021.
41. *Plebeius argus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 ♂, Presnovka, 15.06.2019; 1 ♀, Presnovka, 25.06.2019; 1 ♂, Presnovka, 04.07.2019; 1 ♀, 4 ♂, Presnovka, 11.07.2019; 2 specimens, Shandak, 27.06.2021; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 21.07.2021; 1 specimen, Beskuduk, 04.08.2021; 1 specimen, Korneevka, 06.08.2021.
42. *Plebeius idas* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 11.08.2019; 1 specimen, Korneevka, 06.08.2021.
43. *Polyommatus amandus* (Schneider, 1792) – 2 specimens, Iversk, 09.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 19.06.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 17.06.21.
44. *Polyommatus icarus* (Rottemburg, 1775) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 19.06.2019; 1 ♀, Presnovka, 04.07.2019; 1 specimen, Korneevka, 19.08.2021; 3 ♂, Shandak, 11.07.2021; 1 ♀, Shandak, 2.08.2021; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 24.08.2021.
45. **Polyommatus thersites* (Cantener, 1835) – 1 specimen, Korneevka, 16.07.2021.
46. *Plebeius argyrognomon* (Bergsträsser, 1779) – 1 specimen, Iversk, 14.06.2021.

Family Nymphalidae

47. *Neptis rivularis* (Scopoli, 1763) – 2 specimens, Cherunovka, 15.07.2021; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 16.07.2019; 1 specimen, Yavlenka, 18.07.2021; 2 specimens, Pokrovka, 18.07.2021.

48. *Nymphalis antiopa* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 2 specimens, Meshanskiy forest , 11.04.2019.
49. *Nymphalis xanthomelas* (Esper, 1781) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 07.05.2019.
50. *Aglais urticae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 3 specimens, Budennoe, 07.05.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 15.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 18.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 11.07.19; 2 specimens, Dvinsk, 05.06.2021; 2 specimens, Dzhambul, 15.06.2021; 1 specimens, Novouzenka, 16.06.2021; 3 specimens, Tarangul, 21.06.2021; 1 specimen, Yavlenka, 27.06.2021.
51. *Inachis io* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Meshanskiy forest , 11.04.2019; 1 specimen, Budennoe, 07.05.2019; 2 specimens, Tarangul, 04.06.2021; 2 specimens, Iversk, 28.05.2021; 1 specimen, Dzhambul, 07.06.2021.
52. *Vanessa cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 3 specimens, Dvinsk, 11.06.2019; 2 specimens, Presnovka, 18.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 11.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 24.07.2019; 1 specimen, Yavlenka, 27.06.2021. 1 specimen, Korneevka, 12.07.2021; 3 specimens, Dzhambul, 13.07.2021; 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 19.07.2021; 2 specimens, Tarangul, 20.07.2021.
53. *Araschnia levana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Beskuduk, 08.07.2021; 1♂, Presnovka, 16.07.2019.
54. *Melitaea phoebe* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 04.07.2019; 2 specimens, Presnovka, 11.07.2019.
55. *Brenthis ino* (Rottemburg, 1775) – 1 specimen, Ekaterinovka, 22.07.2019.
56. *Argynnis aglaja* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 10.07.2021.
57. *Vanessa atalanta* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 3 specimens, Tarangul, 16.07.2021; 2 specimens, Beskuduk, 27.07.2021.
58. *Polygonia c-album* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Tarangul, 02.08.2021; 2 specimens, Pokrovka, 10.08.2021; 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 20.08.2021.
59. *Brenthis hecate* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) – 2 specimens, Cherunovka, 15.06.2021.
60. *Issoria lathonia* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Iversk, 03.07.2021.
61. *Argynnis adippe* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Tarangul, 25.06.2019; 1 specimen, Beskuduk, 02.08.2021.
62. *Argynnis paphia* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Tarangul, 12.06.2021; 2 specimens, Korneevka 06.08.2021.
63. *Clossiana dia* (Linnaeus, 1767) – 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 12.08.2021.
64. *Clossiana euphrosyne* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Tarangul, 02.07.2019.

Family Satyridae

65. *Melanargia russiae* (Esper, 1783) – 4 specimens, Ekaterinovka, 17.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 27.06.2021; 3 specimens, Tarangul, 28.06.2021; 4 specimens, Cherunovka, 24.07.2021; 1 specimen, Dzhambul, 30.07.2021.

66. *Coenonympha pamphilus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 16.06.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 09.06.2021; 3 specimens, Yavlenka, 29.07.21; 2 specimens, Shandak, 2.08.2021; 1 specimen, Pokrovka, 06.08.2021.
67. *Coenonympha glycerion* (Borkhausen, 1788) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 05.07.2019; 2 specimens, Shandak, 27.06.2021; 1 specimen, Beskuduk, 04.08.2021.
68. *Aphantopus hyperantus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 15.06.2019.
69. *Hyponephele lycaon* (Rottemburg, 1775) – 2♂, Ekaterinovka, 17.07.2019; 1♂, Shandak, 24.07.2019; 1♀, Shandak, 05.08.2019; 2 specimens, Iversk, 19.07.2021; 2 specimens, Shandak, 19.07.2021; 1 specimen, Shandak, 3.08.2021; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 07.08.2021; 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 12.08.2021.
70. *Minois dryas* (Scopoli, 1763) – 2♂, Ekaterinovka, 17.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 24.07.2019; 2 specimens, Shandak, 11.07.2021; 2 specimens, Iversk, 04.08.2021; 3 specimens, Tarangul, 08.08.2021; 1 specimen, Dzhambul, 14.08.2021.
71. *Coenonympha amaryllis* (Stoll, 1782) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 27.06.2021.
72. *Chazara briseis* (Linnaeus, 1764) – 1 specimen, Iversk, 02.08.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 3.08.2021, 1 specimen, Tarangul, 24.08.2021.
73. *Hipparchia autonoe* (Esper, 1783) – 2 specimens, Dzhambul, 03.08.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 5.07.2021; 3 specimens, Iversk, 12.08.2021; 1 specimen, Korneevka, 13.08.2021.

Family Drepanidae

74. *Falcaria lacertinaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 2 specimens, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
75. *Tethea or* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 28.07.2019.
76. *Achlya flavicornis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 13.04.2019.

Family Geometridae

77. **Archiearis parthenias* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 11.04.2019; 1 male, Petropavlovsk, 11.04.2022, S.A. Knyazev leg.
78. *Selenia lunularia* (Hübner, 1788) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 20.06.2019.
79. *Ennomos autumnaria* (Werneburg, 1859) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 10.08.2019.
80. *Angerona prunaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019.
81. **Chariaspilates formosaria* (Eversmann, 1837) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019.
82. *Hypoxystis pluvialria* (Fabricius, 1787) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
83. *Siona lineata* (Scopoli, 1763) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 17.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 19.06.2019.
84. *Cleora cinctaria* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 4 specimens, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
85. *Ascotis selenaria* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.

86. *Hypomecis roboraria* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 18.06.2019.
87. *Ematurga atomaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 06.06.2019.
88. *Heliomata glarearia* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019.
89. *Tephrina murinaria* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 3 specimens, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
90. *Chiasmia clathrata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 08.05.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 15.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 17.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 08.07.2021; 1 specimen, Cherunovka, 05.06.21.
91. *Gypsochroa renitidata* (Hübner, 1817) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 26.06.2019.
92. *Thalera fimbrialis* (Scopoli, 1763) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 25.06.2019; 2 specimens, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
93. *Chlorissa viridata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 24.06.2019.
94. *Thetidia smaragdaria* (Fabricius, 1787) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 19.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
95. *Lithostege farinata* (Hufnagel, 1767) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
96. *Scotopteryx chenopodiata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 3 specimens, Presnovka, 26.07.2019;
97. *Xanthorhoe fluctuata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 08.05.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 03.08.2019.
98. *Epirrhoe alternata* (Müller, 1764) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 19.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019.
99. *Pelurga comitata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019; 3 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
100. *Eulithis mellinata* (Fabricius, 1787) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 03.07.2019.
101. *Lampropteryx suffumata* (Fabricius, 1787) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019.
102. *Eupithecia succenturiata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019.
103. *Idaea aureolaria* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 19.06.19; 1 specimen, Shandak, 03.08.2019.
104. *Scopula immorata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 19.06.2019.
105. *Timandra comae* (Schmidt, 1931) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 03.08.2019.
106. *Lythria purpuraria* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 2 specimens, Iversk, 05.08.2021; 2 specimens, Tarangul, 09.08.2021; 1 specimen, Dzhambul, 17.08.2021; 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 07.08.2021.

Family Lasiocampidae

107. *Malacosoma neustria* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 22.07.19.

108. *Euthrix potatoria* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1♂, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1♂, Ekaterinovka, to the light trap, 19.07.2019.
109. *Gastropacha quercifolia* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 12.07.2019.
110. *Phyllodesma tremulifolium* (Hübner, 1803-1808) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 14.07.2019.
111. *Odonestis pruni* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1♂, Presnovka, 05.07.2019.

Family Endromididae

112. *Endromis versicolora* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 02.05.2019.

Family Sphingidae

113. *Laothoe populi* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 18.07.2021; 1 specimen, Ekaterinovka, 22.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 24.07.2019.
114. *Smerinthus ocellatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 8.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
115. *Mimas tiliae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 3.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
116. *Hyles euphorbiae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 10.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 07.08.2019.
117. *Deilephila elpenor* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019.
118. *Choerocampa porcellus* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 05.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 17.07.2021; 2 specimens, Cherunovka, 22.07.2021; 1 specimen, Korneevka, 27.08.2021.

Family Notodontidae

119. *Clostera albosigma* (Fitch, 1855) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 08.05.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, to the light trap, 14.07.2019.

Family Lymantriidae

120. *Euproctis similis* (Fuessly, 1775) – 3 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019.
121. *Leucoma salicis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 06.06.2019.

Family Arctiidae

122. *Collita griseola* (Hübner, 1803) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 22.07.2019.
123. **Manulea complana* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.

124. *Spiris striata* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 18.06.2019.
125. *Arctia caja* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1♂, Ekaterinovka, 19.07.2019; 1♂, Ekaterinovka, to the light trap, 22.07.19; 1♂, Shandak, 23.07.2019; 1♀, Shandak, 30.07.19; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 17.07.2021.
126. *Arctia flavia* (Fuessly, 1779) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1 specimen, Ekaterinovka, to the light trap, 22.07.2019; 1♂, 1♀, Shandak, 24.07.2019.
127. *Epicallia villica* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 17.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 18.06.2019; 2 specimens, Beskuduk, 24.07.2021.
128. *Diacrisia sannio* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 18.06.2019.
129. *Phragmatobia fuliginosa* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.19; 1 specimen, Shandak, 14.07.2019.
130. *Spilarctia luteum* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 06.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 18.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 06.07.2019; 2♂, 2♀, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
131. *Spilosoma lubricipedum* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 06.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 17.06.19; 1 specimen, Shandak, 18.06.2019; 2 specimens, Presnovka, 20.06.2019.

Family Erebidae

132. **Hypena rostralis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 08.05.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019.
133. **Eublemma amasina* (Eversmann, 1842) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 24.06.2019.
134. *Catocala nupta* (Linnaeus, 1767) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 25.07.2019.
135. **Catocala fulminea* (Scopoli, 1763) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 22.07.2019.
136. *Euclidia glyphica* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019; 1 specimen, Dvinsk, 03.08.2021.
137. **Lygephila lubrica* (Freyer, 1842) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019.
138. *Lygephila ludicra* (Hübner, 1790) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
139. **Lygephila pastinum* (Treitschke, 1826) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019.

Family Nolidae

140. *Nola aerugula* (Hübner, 1793) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.08.2019.
141. *Earias clorana* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 05.07.2019.

Family Noctuidae

142. *Diachrysis stenochrysis* (Warren, 1913) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 20.06.2019; 1 specimen, Ekaterinovka, 22.07.2019.
143. *Autographa gamma* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 30.05.2019; 3 specimens, Novouzenka, 06.08.2021; 2 specimens, Tarangul, 21.08.2021.

144. **Autographa mandarina* (Freyer, 1845) – 1 specimen, Novouzenka, 12.07.2021; 2 specimens, Iversk, 28.08.2021.
145. *Plusia festucae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 14.07.2019.
146. *Plusia putnami* (Grote, 1873) ssp.festata (Graeser, 1889) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 22.07.2019.
147. *Deltote bankiana* (Fabricius, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019.
148. *Acontia lucida* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 10.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019.
149. *Acontia trabealis* (Scopoli, 1763) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 03.07.2019; 2 specimens, Ekaterinovka, 22.07.2019.
150. **Aedia funesta* (Esper, 1786) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1 specimen, Ekaterinovka, 22.07.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 21.06.2021.
151. **Acrionicta euphorbiae* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 25.07.2019.
152. **Simyra albovenosa* (Goeze, 1781) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
153. *Mycteropus puniceago* (Boisduval, 1840) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019.
154. *Tyta luctuosa* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 10.08.2019.
155. **Cucullia splendida* (Fabricius, 1787) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.08.2019.
156. **Cucullia fraudatrix* (Eversmann, 1837) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 25.07.2019.
157. *Cucullia inderiensis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1856) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 13.04.2019.
158. *Cucullia pustulata* (Eversmann, 1842) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 14.07.19.
159. **Cucullia lucifuga* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.19.
160. *Cucullia umbratica* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
161. *Cucullia fuchsiana* (Eversmann, 1842) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
162. *Brachionycha nubeculosa* (Esper, 1785) – 1 specimen, Meshanskiy forest, 11.04.2019; 2 specimens, Budennoe, 13.04.19; 2 specimens, Budennoe, 22.04.2019.
163. *Pyrrhia umbra* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 16.07.2019.
164. *Heliothis viriplaca* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 1 specimen, Tarangul, 02.08.2021; 1 specimen, Cherunovka, 22.08.2021.
165. **Heliothis maritima* (Graslin, 1855) – 1 specimen, Iversk, 04.08.2021.
166. *Eucarta virgo* (Treitschke, 1835) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 28.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
167. *Pseudeustrotia candidula* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 10.07.2019.
168. *Caradrina morpheus* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 4 specimens, Presnovka, 28.06.2019; 2 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.

169. *Trachea atriplicis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
170. *Amphipoea fucosa* (Freyer, 1830) – 2 specimens, Ekaterinovka, 22.07.2019; 3 specimens, Tarangul, 12.08.2021.
171. *Nonagria typhae* (Thunberg, 1784) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 25.07.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019.
172. **Apamea furva* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 28.06.19; 1 specimen, Ekaterinovka, 22.07.2019.
173. *Apamea lateritia* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 15 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
174. *Apamea sordens* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 3 specimens, Presnovka, 28.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
175. *Oligia latruncula* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 28.07.2019.
176. *Resapamea vulpecula* (Eversmann, 1852) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
177. *Conistra rubiginea* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 20.04.2019.
178. *Conistra vaccinii* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 5 specimens, Budennoe, 20.04.2019; 1 specimen, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
179. **Orbona fragariae* (Vieweg, 1790) – 1 specimen, Meshanskiy forest , 11.04.2019.
180. **Orthosia gracilis* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
181. *Orthosia incerta* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 17 specimens, Budennoe, 20.04.2019; 4 specimens, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
182. *Orthosia opima* (Hübner, 1809) – 2 specimens, Budennoe, 13.04.2019; 3 specimens, Budennoe, 22.04.2019.
183. *Tholera decimalis* (Poda, 1761) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019; 1 specimen, Dvinsk, 28.08.2021.
184. **Anarta dianthii* (Tauscher, 1809) – 3 specimens, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
185. **Anarta stigmosa* (Christoph, 1887) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 06.07.2019.
186. *Anarta trifolii* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 3 specimens, Budennoe, 08.05.2019; 3 specimens, Presnovka, 09.07.2019; 3 specimens, Presnovka, 25.07.2019.
187. *Polia nebulosa* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 03.07.2019.
188. *Lacanobia contigua* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 08.05.2019.
189. *Lacanobia oleracea* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
190. *Lacanobia suasa* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Budennoe, 08.05.2019; 2 specimens, Budennoe, 28.06.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 28.07.2019.
191. *Lacanobia thalassina* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 18.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 28.06.2019.

192. **Melanchra persicariae* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
193. *Hyssia cavernosa* (Eversmann, 1842) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019.
194. **Mamestra brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 31.05.2019.
195. *Conisania luteago* (Lederer, 1855) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 30.07.2019.
196. *Hecatera bicolorata* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 1 specimen, c. Shandak, 08.07.2019.
197. **Hecatera dysodea* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 28.07.2019.
198. *Mythimna conigera* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Ekaterinovka, 22.07.2019.
199. *Mythimna deserticola* (Bartel, 1903) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019.
200. *Mythimna impura* (Hübner, 1808) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 10.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
201. *Mythimna pallens* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 10.07.2019.
202. **Mythimna turca* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
203. *Mythimna velutina* (Eversmann, 1846) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 03.07.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 26.07.2019.
204. *Euxoa nigricans* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 25.07.2019; 1 specimen, Tarangul, 26.08.2021.
205. *Euxoa ochrogaster* (Guenée, 1852) – 1 specimen, Beskuduk, 23.08.2021.
206. *Agrotis exclamationis* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 2 specimens, Budennoe, 31.05.2019; 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 28.06.2019; 2 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
207. *Agrotis segetum* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019.
208. *Axylia putris* (Linnaeus, 1761) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 20.06.19; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 12.07.19.
209. *Noctua interposita* (Hübner, 1790) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 10.08.2019.
210. *Cryptocala chardinyi* (Boisduval, 1829) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 05.07.2019.
211. *Eurois occulta* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 06.06.2019; 1 specimen, Presnovka, 20.06.2019.
212. *Xestia c-nigrum* (Linnaeus, 1758) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 18.06.2019; 2 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
213. *Xestia ditrapezium* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775) – 2 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
214. *Xestia triangulum* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 1 specimen, Presnovka, 06.07.2019; 5 specimens, Presnovka, 12.07.2019.
215. **Protolampra sobrina* (Duponchel, 1843) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 21.06.2019.
216. *Pseudohermonassa melanholica* (Staudinger, 1897) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 19.06.2019.
217. **Graphiphora augur* (Fabricius, 1775) – 1 specimen, Shandak, 08.07.2019.
218. *Cirrhia icteritia* (Hufnagel, 1766) – 2 specimens, Iversk, 22.08.2021.

Family Zygaenidae

219. *Zygaena osterodensis* (Reiss, 1921) – 1 specimen, Dzhambul, 28.07.2021.

Thus, the list of Lepidoptera of the region has been replenished with 37 new species. The total number of species known from the territory of the North Kazakhstan region is 557. New data on the distribution of already known species from other territories of the region were also obtained.

Acknowledgements

Authors thank Kristina A. Mifodovskaya (Petropavlovsk, Kazakhstan) for the materials provided for our study. The work was supported by the Altai State University in the framework of the federal project “Priority-2030”.

References

- Knyazev SA (2015) The list of Lepidoptera (Insecta, Lepidoptera) of Northern Kazakhstan. Amurian zoological journal 7 (4): 325–331. [In Russian]
- Knyazev SA, Zuban IA (2016) The list of Lepidoptera (Insecta, Lepidoptera) of Northern Kazakhstan. Part 2. Amurian zoological journal 8 (3): 199–208. [In Russian]
- Knyazev SA, Zuban IA (2019) The list of Lepidoptera (Insecta, Lepidoptera) of Northern Kazakhstan. Part 3. Acta Biologica Sibirica 5 (1): 133–140. <https://doi.org/10.14258/abs.v5.i1.5348> [In Russian]
- Sinev SYu (ed.) (2019) Catalog of Lepidoptera of Russia. Edition 2. Zoological Institute of RAS, Saint Petersburg, 448 pp. [In Russian]